

THE ROLE OF VOCABULARY IN LEARNING ENGLISH

Jo'rayeva E'tiborkhon

Teacher, UzSWLU

miss.attention97@gmail.com

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Abstract: This article introduces the importance of vocabulary in English and the methods used by teachers as well as including my own theory.

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Importance of vocabulary:

One of the most crucial micro skills to master when learning a foreign language is expanding one's personal vocabulary. All micro-skills, including grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation, are crucial. However, communicating without a vocabulary is much more challenging than communicating without a grammar. In order to understand and create texts that are ever-more complex, children need to have a broad vocabulary that keeps expanding through language and literacy experiences. They also need to use vocal language for a range of social functions. In order to assist their verbal and writing communication, it is essential that children get explicit and thorough vocabulary education. Students can access academic language and discourse thanks to the explicit instruction of vocabulary, which also makes it easier for them to understand texts that are getting more and more complicated. In addition, In order to communicate properly, we need to have a certain vocabulary. The four vocabularies that educators frequently take into account are hearing, speaking, reading, and writing. The words we require to comprehend what we hear are referred to as listening vocabulary. The words we use when we speak make up our spoken vocabulary. The words we require to understand what we read are known as reading vocabulary. The words we employ in writing make up our writing vocabulary. Reading comprehension is greatly aided by vocabulary. The words they hear verbally must be used in conjunction with the ones they read in print for beginning readers. Children who hear more words spoken at home pick up more words and come to school with better vocabularies. Take a look at what happens, for instance, when a novice reader comes across the term "dig" in a book. The reader realizes that the sounds in the letters d, l and g make form a very well-known word that she has heard and spoken numerous times as she starts to decipher the sounds represented by the letters. Learning words that are unfamiliar to them from their oral (spoken) vocabulary is more difficult for a beginning reader. Reading comprehension depends on vocabulary. Without understanding the meaning of the majority of the words, readers cannot comprehend what they are reading. Children must acquire the definitions of new terms that are not already a part of their speech vocabulary as they go to reading increasingly complex books.

Vocabulary-building techniques:

1. Read a lot, and read everything.

Your vocabulary will grow if you read frequently, both within and outside of the classroom. Keep a running note of words you do not know every time you read something in a book, magazine, newspaper, blog, or any other source. Incorporate the words into your own speaking and writing by looking them up when you come across them.

2. Construct index cards.

Try creating flashcards for review if you are learning certain words for a test or if you know specific phrases will be used frequently in the subject or field you are studying. Make sure to include both the meaning and the word for each essential keyword on one side of an index card. Self-examine, followed by a friend-assisted test.

3. Set a goal.

- If you are serious about increasing your vocabulary, give yourself a target to work toward. To incorporate three new terms into your speech and writing, try learning one new word per week. Thousands of new words that you will remember and use can be learned if you put in the effort. A word does not belong in your vocabulary if you cannot use it correctly and efficiently in a sentence.
- Start raising the stakes if you can effortlessly pick up three new words each week. Try to pick up ten words the next week.
- It will be tough to use any of them correctly if you look up 20 new terms a day in the dictionary. Keep your expectations in check and develop a useful vocabulary.

Difficulties while learning vocabulary

The pupils have trouble selecting the right word meanings, and they are still uncertain about how to use a word in a certain situation. When they came across idiomatic phrases or expressions, the students were still perplexed. There were a few things that made it challenging for kids to learn language. The number of words that students need to learn is extremely enormous, there are few reliable sources of information on terms, and word knowledge is difficult, therefore the written form of English differs from the spoken form. Knowing a word requires much more than simply knowing its definition from a dictionary. Incorrect pronunciation is frequently brought on by a lack of phonological similarity between English and the students' native tongue.

Teacher`s role and their teaching approaches:

Giving instructions is not the only aspect of teaching. It deals with how to construct approaches, activities, and lesson plans for teaching language components, as well as how to motivate students to engage in these activities. As one of the key players in the teaching and learning processes, the teacher therefore plays a crucial role. However, the teacher must have extensive training in professional skills, psycholinguistics, and applied linguistics. The teacher must comprehend the nature of the language he is teaching due to his linguistic abilities. Additionally, he should be able to utilize it, which means that when it appears in the texts to be taught, he should be able to produce and comprehend the vocabulary words and phrases that are appropriate in a certain situation. The teacher should possess a substantial quantity of information about the psychology of learning and theories of teaching and learning languages due to psycholinguistics and professional skills. Additionally, the teacher needs to be familiar with some language teaching strategies. The instructor has to be proficient with instructional tools. Any English language training must include the instruction of vocabulary. Concerns concerning vocabulary instruction are common among teachers. The introduction of new terms must be done in a way that would grab the students' interest and help them remember the words. In order to advance in their language learning, students must be familiar with methods for memorization of significant amounts of new vocabulary. It is common to think of acquiring English vocabulary as a tedious process of memorizing lists of unconnected terms. To study and teach vocabulary in an EFL setting, there are numerous

additional, much more effective and engaging approaches. For teaching vocabulary, teachers can use tools like word cards or simple flashcards. A statement comprising the term, its description, synonyms, and pronunciation is written on one side of the card by the teacher, and the English language word is written on the other. A great memory aid is a deck of word cards. Students can use this as a convenient way to bring their newly learned vocabulary around with them and review it anytime they have the chance. The word association technique is an additional effective vocabulary-building strategy. Words that are stored separately are more challenging to recall because they lack context. However, the words are more easily retained if they are group together in sentences and phrases that are frequently used. This method of pairing collocational terms with one another enables pupils to connect related words.

It is an ongoing endeavor for both teachers and students to teach and learn language. Thus, the primary focus of programs for teaching and learning languages should be on vocabulary instruction.

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